

Removal of copper from wastewater using rice polish (rice bran)

K. K. Singh and S. H. Hasan*

Water Pollution Research Laboratory, Department of Applied Chemistry, Institute of Technology,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, India

E-mail : hasanitbhu@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 13 August 2004, accepted 24 November 2004

Rice polish has been successfully utilized for the removal of copper(II) from wastewater. The maximum removal of copper(II) has been found to be 97.5% at pH 8.0, initial Cu^{II} concentration 125 mg L⁻¹ and temperature 20°C. The effect of different parameters are similar to that of cadmium sorption as described in the previous paper.

The presence of metal ions in natural or industrial wastewater and their potential impact has been a subject of research in environmental science for a long time. Metal ions such as cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, zinc and iron are commonly detected in both natural and industrial effluents. In continuation of our work on adsorption of heavy metals from wastewater, in this present study we have chosen rice polish (rice bran) for the removal of Cu^{II} from wastewater, which is cheap, easily available and mostly biodegradable¹.

Materials and methods :

Physico-chemical analysis of the adsorbent :

Rice polish (rice bran) is a byproduct of rice milling plant. It was collected from M/s. Manoj Industries (rice mill), Chunar, Mirzapur (U.P.) and was used in experiments with double washing with double-distilled water to remove soluble lighter materials and drying at 60°C in an oven and crushing and sieving to < 178 µm.

Various physical properties of rice polish are given in Table 1. Chemical analysis of the rice polish shows the presence of various oxides of Ca, Si, Mn, Mg and Fe etc. X-Ray diffraction and IR studies show that major constituents of rice polish are carbon while quartz, carbon hexagonal, Fe-O, Mg-O, Mn-O, Ca-O, Si-C, CaSiO₃, Ca₂SiO₄ and Ca-P have been found (18.44%).

Experimental procedure was same as in an earlier communication. In place of maize bran, rice polish has been used in this present case and cadmium chloride was replaced with copper(II) sulphate.

Results and discussion

Effect of contact time and concentration :

A series of experiments were performed at different initial adsorbate concentration viz. 100, 125 and 150 mg L⁻¹ and time interval and at a temperature of 30°C and pH 8.0. The percentage removal of Cu^{II} was found 97.1, 92.2 and 85.6, respectively. The nature and extent of adsorption was similar as in case of cadmium(II) adsorption¹. Adsorption dynamics, mass transfer analysis, effect of temperature, adsorption isotherm and effect of pH are all similar to cadmium adsorption in maize bran. Data for adsorption rate constants, thermodynamic parameters and percentage removal of copper are given in Tables 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 1. Physical and chemical properties of biosorbent rice polish

Surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	452.00
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	0.3010
Particle size (µm)	< 178
Average particle diameter (cm)	1.74 × 10 ⁻²
Porosity (fraction)	0.39
Proximate analysis (%) :	
Moisture	8.3
Volatile matter	43.12
Fixed carbon	30.14
Ash (oxides of Ca, Mn, Si, Fe, Mg etc.)	18.44

Modelling :

Models play a key role in transferring technologies from the laboratories to a full-scale application. Good models cannot only help in analyzing the experimental data but also in predicting the response of the systems to changing conditions.

Table 2. Adsorption rate constants for Cu^{II} at different temperatures

Temp (°C)	k_{ad} (min ⁻¹)	k_{id} (mg g ⁻¹ , min ^{-1/2})	\bar{D} (cm ² s ⁻¹)	β_1 (cm s ⁻¹)
20	6.086×10^{-2}	1.22×10^{-2}	8.321×10^{-9}	6.897×10^{-5}
30	5.718×10^{-2}	1.04×10^{-2}	7.433×10^{-9}	6.485×10^{-5}
40	5.371×10^{-2}	8.36×10^{-3}	5.748×10^{-9}	5.931×10^{-5}

Table 3. Values of thermodynamic parameters, Langmuir constants and R_L for adsorption of Cu^{II} on rice polish at different temperatures

Temp. (°C)	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\circ$ (cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Q^0 (mg g ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	R_L
20	2.059	18.602	56.512	142.72	0.962	0.0112
30	1.501			140.68	0.654	0.0146
40	1.125	11.871	34.315	135.46	0.408	0.0172

Table 4. Percentage removal at different conditions on experimental and predicted values at equilibrium time, pH 8.0 and agitation rate 125 rpm

Initial adsorbate concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Percentage removal		Temp. (°C)	Percentage removal	
	Expt. value	Predicted value		Expt. value	Predicted value
100	97.1	97.16	20	97.5	94.24
125	92.2	90.50	30	92.2	90.50
150	85.6	86.06	40	86.3	86.76

Empirical model :

In order to find out the rate of removal of Cu^{II} from wastewater by rice polish, the following empirical mathematical model has been developed between contact time (min) and initial and remaining concentration C_0 and C_t (both in mg L⁻¹) of Cu^{II} respectively.

$$\log(t + 1) = K(C_0 - C_t)^A \quad (1)$$

where K and A are constants. The following relations for different C_0 , have been found.

$$\text{For } C_0 = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}; \log(t + 1) = 0.4723(C_0 - C_t)^{0.7849} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{For } C_0 = 125 \text{ mg L}^{-1}; \log(t + 1) = 0.5559(C_0 - C_t)^{0.7635} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{For } C_0 = 150 \text{ mg L}^{-1}; \log(t + 1) = 0.6069(C_0 - C_t)^{0.7472} \quad (4)$$

The values of A and K are determined from the slope and

intercept of the plot $\log[\log(t + 1)]$ vs $\log(C_0 - C_t)$. The plots of $\log(t + 1)$ vs $(C_0 - C_t)^A$ are linear in each case showing the applicability of the above model.

The log-log plot of K and C_0 gives a straight line having the following relationship :

$$K = 0.0865 C_0^{0.7689} \quad (5)$$

The plot of A and C_0 also gives straight line having the following relationship :

$$A = 0.8591 - 0.0008C_0 \quad (6)$$

The applicability of the proposed model is helpful to calculate the amount of Cu^{II} adsorbed by this adsorbent.

Multiple regression analysis :

We have seen the effect of initial adsorbate concentration, contact time, temperature and pH of the system on Cu^{II} removal by rice polish. The cumulative effect of all these independent variables (copper removal) are given by the following relation :

$$Y = 6.5594 + 0.6384a_1 + 0.5169a_2 - 0.4680a_3 + 0.2834a_4 - 0.0622a_5 \quad (7)$$

where, Y is the predicted value of Cu^{II} removal; a_1 , concentration of adsorbate; a_2 , contact time; a_3 , temperature; a_4 , pH; a_5 , agitation rate of the system. The model values calculated with the help of eq. (7) and the experimental values are given in the Table 4. It may be seen that predicted values are pretty close to the experimental values. From these results it is concluded that all independent variables have cumulative effect on the copper removal by rice polish.

Conclusion :

The rice polish has been found to be a very effective biosorbent for the efficient removal of Cu^{II} from wastewater. The maximum removal of copper(II) has been found to be 97.5% at pH 8.0, initial Cu^{II} concentration 125 mg L⁻¹ and temperature 20°C. In all copper(II) adsorption on rice bran is exactly similar to cadmium adsorption in maize bran.

Reference

1. K. K. Singh, D. C. Rupainwar and S. H. Hasan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 342.